

**DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF TEACHING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS ON
THE BASE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES**

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Annotation . In the article general professional science didactic teaching of improvement approaches suitable respectively done increase , data digital technologies based on to express and their more clearer , simpler in appearance to describe service to do about word goes

Key words : digital educational technologies, strategy, modeling, dynamic environment, motivation .

Today, different opinions are expressed about the teaching of professional subjects and its place in the higher education system. In our opinion, the science of quantitative methods in higher education is considered not only the main discipline, but also one of the most important components of the culture of the individual, the achievements in the development of the science are the reason for the serious development of the worldview both materially and spiritually [1].

Studying the topic of evaluation of actions and errors in the conscious and deep mastery of science creates a number of difficulties for students. With this, students' demands for modern education and digital educational technologies will increase. These activities, in turn, should include the necessary conditions for the development of skillful use of digital technologies. However, the use of digital learning technologies requires the ability to perform many elements. Without denying the advantages of using this type of digital technologies, it should be noted that familiarity with them often has the character of passive thinking, which encourages the independent search for certain relationships.

The wide use of digital educational technologies in the educational process allows to increase the effectiveness of educational and educational work, to further increase the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. A change in the thinking methodology, forms and methods of all kinds of educational activities is inevitable, and therefore there are certain advantages and at the same time certain problems. Solving these problems occupies one of the central places in the theory and practice of teaching today. In this regard, the strategy of using digital technologies as a teaching tool in the educational process, as well as in the development of the methodology for the full implementation of appropriate educational programs for their use, require certain adjustments [2].

Today's education system is at its current stage and management of this system cannot be imagined without the use of digital technologies. The use of digital technologies in the educational process is an urgent requirement for modern society. The use of digital technologies in the educational process allows to reduce the burden on the student, to increase the quality of teaching, and at the same time, it serves to make the educational process more culturally, scientifically and creatively interesting.

By carrying out the technological process of preparation for professional activity : lectures and practical trainings are formed using fully modern technologies ; pre-prepared presentations, video lectures and animations are used for training; the materials prepared by the

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teacher are of great importance to the students' perfect education. The training is aimed at a specific goal and is managed by the teacher, as a result of which skills and competencies are formed based on the knowledge obtained from the theoretical lessons necessary to perform a specific task. Independent in education teacher by prepared materials students individually they learn .

The didactic possibilities of using digital educational technologies are decisive and depend on the correct and perfect organization of the educational process by students. Using software-pedagogical tools, the teacher is obliged to determine in which order it is appropriate to use them during the lesson in order to stimulate the mental activity of students in each specific case.

The link "Resource type - student's actions - teacher's management actions" is reflected in the table below .

Electronic resource type	Software from the product use according to of students actions	Teacher's management actions
Information reference	Perception about information . Traditional study (from class except) tasks solution to do for helper information (text , image , music).	Electronic resources choose area create them search organize do , information perception reach in the process to students advice to give
Instrumental - practical	Information objects practical design , real processes models Create and analysis to do	Students software products with mutually in communications advice and pedagogical help to give
Educational assessment	Computer command with actions perform Computer results based on done increased actions reflection carry on and management	Digital electron from the resource pedagogical in terms of to the goal according to to use organize to achieve
Complex	Education (from class except) tasks solution to do for each different kind of digital electron of resources to the combination based on himself learning	Study programs and addition education programs work exit with electron of resources to use synchronization .

Our research shows that the highest came alive m u amm o l a r n i n g The solution is for teachers j a r a y o n i d a f o y d a l a n i l a d i g a n [11-15] modern technologies and knowledge In conclusion, modeling of the process of change in our studied science with the help of digital technologies allows us to highlight their features through observation. Increasing students' motivation, training basic abilities and skills creates qualitatively new didactic opportunities.

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